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O‘ZGARUVCHILI KOEFFITSIENTLI NOCHIZIQLI YUQORI TARTIBLI INTEGRO – DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR TIZIMLARINI SONLI YECHISHNING MATEMATIK APPARATI VA DASTURIY TA’MINOTI

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***Annotatsiya:** Maqolada o‘zgaruvchili koeffitsientli nochiziqli yuqori tartibli integro-differensial tenglamalar tizimlarini kvadratura formulalarini qo‘llashga asoslangan sonli usul hamda Mathcad kompyuter matematikasi tizimi vositasida sonli yechish matematik apparati va dasturiy ta‘minoti keltirilgan.*

***Аннотация:** В статье приведена математический аппарат и программное обеспечение для численного решения систем нелинейных интегро-дифференциальных уравнений высших порядков с переменными коэффициентами численным методом, основанным на использование квадратурных формул средствами систем компьютерной математики Mathcad.*

***Abstract:** The article presents the mathematical apparatus and software for the numerical solution of systems of nonlinear integro-differential equations of higher orders with variable coefficients using a numerical method based on the use of quadrature formulas using Mathcad computer mathematics systems.*

***Kalit so‘zlar:** integro-differensial tenglamalar, matematik apparat, Mathcad, Maple, kompyuter matematikasi, dasturlash.*

KIRISH

Metallurgiya sanoati, tog‘-kon sanoati, paxtachilik sanoati, to‘qimachilik sanoati, umuman olganda og‘ir va yengil sanoat mashina-mexanizmlari, boshqacha aytganda qattiq jismlar mexanikasining plastinka va qobiq tipidagi yupqa devorli konstruksiyalarining dinamik tebranishlari harakat tenglamalari ayrim hollarda fazoviy o‘zgaruvchilar bo‘yicha diskretizatsiyalash usullaridan biri qo‘llanilgandan keyin chiziqli integro-differensial tenglamalar sistemasiga keltirish mumkin.

ADABIYOTLAR TAHLILI VA METOLOGİYASI

Integral va integro-differensial tenglamalar sonli yechish usullari [1]da keltirilgan. Kompyuter matematikasi, kompyuter industriyasi va dasturlash texnologiyalarining jadal suratlar bilan rivojlanishi ta‘lim-tarbiya, ilmiy-metodik va

ilmiy tadqiqot ishlarini avtomatlashtirishning asosi sifatida e'tirof etilmoqda. Zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalari sohasida qo'lga kiritilgan yutuqlarni qo'llash natijasida ilmiy-tadqiqot, ilmiy-metodik, ilmiy-texnik, injenerlik, moliyaviy va iqtisodiy, kimyoviy, biologik masalalarni yechishni avtomatlashtirish tomon yo'naltirilgan ko'plab dasturiy vositalar mavjuddir. Masalan: Mathematica, Maple, Matlab, Mathcad, Derive, Scientific, Workplce, Femlab, FeexPDE kabi universal dasturiy muhitlar shular jumlasidandir. Bulardan ikkitasi Mathematica, Maple[2] professional matematiklar va ilmiy-tadqiqotlar olib boruvchi mutaxassislar tomonidan keng qo'llanilmoqda. Mathcad[3] esa injenerlik hisob-kitob ishlarining instrumenti sifatida ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib hozirda yetarlicha murakkablikka ega bo'lgan hisob-kitoblarni bajarishda, ilmiy-tekshirish ishlarida har xil sonli algoritmlarni va analitik almashtirishni bajarishda foydalanilmoqda[4].

Chiziqli va nochiziqli integro-differensial tenglamalar va ularning tizimlarini sonli yechishning samarali usullaridan biri professor F. Badalov tomonidan taklif etilgan "Kvadratura formulalarini qo'llashga asoslangan sonli usul" [1] hisoblanadi. Bu usulning mohiyati shundan iboratki, tenglamaga kiruvchi integrallar kvadratura formulalari yordamida chekli summalarga almashtiriladi va algebraik tenglamalar tizimlariga keltiriladi.

NATIJALAR:

Ushbu maqolada to'rtinchi tartibli nochiziqli o'zgaruvchi koeffitsientli integro – differensial tenglamalar tizimii qaraladi:

$$a_1 \left(\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^4} x(t) \right) + a_2 \left(\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^4} y(t) \right) + a_3(t) \left(x(t)^3 - \int_0^t K_1(t-\tau) x(\tau)^3 d\tau \right) \quad (1)$$

$$b_1 \left(\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^4} x(t) \right) + b_2 \left(\frac{\partial^4}{\partial t^4} y(t) \right) + b_3(t) \left(y(t)^3 - \int_0^t K_2(t-\tau) y(\tau)^3 d\tau \right)$$

$$\text{boshlang'ich shartlar: } x(0) = A_0, D(x)(0) = A_1, DD(x)(0) = A_2, DDD(x) = A_3$$

(2)

$$y(0) = B_0, D(y)(0) = B_1, DD(y)(0) = B_2, DDD(Y) = B_3$$

bu yerda , $x(t)$, $y(t)$ – izlanayotgan funksiyalar, $f_1(t)$, $f_2(t)$ – berilgan funksiyalar ,

$$K_1(t) = \varepsilon_1 t^{(\alpha_1 - 1)} e^{(-\beta_1 t)}, K_2(t) = \varepsilon_2 t^{(\alpha_2 - 1)} e^{(-\beta_2 t)} \text{-yadrolar}$$

$$a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2, A_0, A_1, A_2, A_3, B_0, B_1, B_2, B_3$$

$$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4 -$$

o‘zgaruvchi parametrli.

(1) to‘rtinchi tartibli o‘zgaruvchi koeffitsientli chiziqli integro-differensial tenglamalar tizimining tenglamalarini to‘rt marta t bo‘yicha integrallab va boshlang‘ich shartlarni hisobga olib :

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_1 x(t) + a_2 y(t) = & \\
 & a_1 A_0 + a_1 A_1 t + \frac{1}{2} a_1 A_2 t^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_1 A_3 t^3 + a_2 B_0 + a_2 B_1 t + \frac{1}{2} a_2 B_2 t^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_2 B_3 t^3 \\
 & + \int_0^t \frac{1}{6} (t - \tau)^3 \left(f_1(\tau) - a_3(\tau) \left(x(\tau)^3 - \int_0^\tau K_1(\tau - z) x(z)^3 dz \right) \right) d\tau
 \end{aligned}$$

(3)

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_1 x(t) + b_2 y(t) = & \\
 & b_1 A_0 + b_1 A_1 t + \frac{1}{2} b_1 A_2 t^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_1 A_3 t^3 + b_2 B_0 + b_2 B_1 t + \frac{1}{2} b_2 B_2 t^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_2 B_3 t^3 \\
 & + \int_0^t \frac{1}{6} (t - \tau)^3 \left(f_2(\tau) - b_3(\tau) \left(y(\tau)^3 - \int_0^\tau K_2(\tau - z) y(z)^3 dz \right) \right) d\tau
 \end{aligned}$$

integral tenglamalar tizimini hosil qilamiz. Bu integral tenglamalar tizimini sonli yechishga “ kvadratura formulalarini qo‘llashga asoslangan sonli usul” [1] ni qo‘llaymiz. Bu usulning mohiyati shundan iboratki, (3) integral tenglamalar tizimiga kiruvchi integrallar kvadratura formulalari yordamida chekli summalarga almashtiriladi :

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_1 x_n + a_2 y_n = & \\
 & a_1 A_0 + a_1 A_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} a_1 A_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_1 A_3 t_n^3 + a_2 B_0 + a_2 B_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} a_2 B_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_2 B_3 t_n^3 \\
 + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} & \left(\frac{1}{6} c_j (t_n - t_j)^3 \left(f_1(t_j) - a_3(t_j) \left(x(t_j)^3 - \frac{\varepsilon_1 \left(\sum_{m=0}^j p_m e^{(-\beta_1 t_m)} x_{j-m}^3 \right)}{\alpha_1} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

(4)

$$\begin{aligned}
 b_1 x_n + b_2 y_n = & \\
 & b_1 A_0 + b_1 A_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} b_1 A_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_1 A_3 t_n^3 + b_2 B_0 + b_2 B_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} b_2 B_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_2 B_3 t_n^3 \\
 + \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} & \left(\frac{1}{6} c_j (t_n - t_j)^3 \left(f_2(t_j) - b_3(t_j) \left(y(t_j)^3 - \frac{\varepsilon_2 \left(\sum_{m=0}^j r_m e^{(-\beta_2 t_m)} y_{j-m}^3 \right)}{\alpha_2} \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

x_n va y_n integral tenglamalar tizimi yechimlarining t_n tugun nuqtalardagi qiymatlari, c_j , p_m , r_m lar kvadratura formulari koeffitsientlari. (4) tizimda quyidagi belgilashlar kiritamiz:

$$w_n = a_1 A_0 + a_1 A_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} a_1 A_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_1 A_3 t_n^3 + a_2 B_0 + a_2 B_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} a_2 B_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} a_2 B_3 t_n^3$$

$$+ \left(\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{1}{6} c_j (t_n - t_j)^3 \left(f_1(t_j) - a_3(t_j) \left(x(t_j)^3 - a_3(t_j) \left(x(t_j)^3 - \frac{\varepsilon_1 \left(\sum_{m=0}^j p_m e^{(-\beta_1 t_m)} x_{j-m}^3 \right)}{\alpha_1} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$v_n = b_1 A_0 + b_1 A_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} b_1 A_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_1 A_3 t_n^3 + b_2 B_0 + b_2 B_1 t_n + \frac{1}{2} b_2 B_2 t_n^2 + \frac{1}{6} b_2 B_3 t_n^3$$

$$+ \left(\sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \left(\frac{1}{6} c_j (t_n - t_j)^3 \left(f_1(t_j) - b_3(t_j) \left(y(t_j)^3 - b_3(t_j) \left(y(t_j)^3 - \frac{\varepsilon_2 \left(\sum_{m=0}^j p_m e^{(-\beta_2 t_m)} y_{j-m}^3 \right)}{\alpha_2} \right) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

U holda (4) tizim

$$a_1 x_n + a_2 y_n = w_n \tag{5}$$

$$b_1 x_n + b_2 y_n = v_n$$

(5) ko‘rinishga keladi, bu tizimni yechib :

$$x_n = \frac{b_2 w_n - a_2 v_n}{a_1 b_2 - a_2 b_1}, \tag{6}$$

$$y_n = \frac{b_1 w_n - a_1 v_n}{a_2 b_1 - a_1 b_2}$$

larni topamiz.

MUHOKAMA.

Shunday qilib, berilgan (1) tizim tenglamalarini to‘rt marta t bo‘yicha integrallab va boshlang‘ich shartlarni hisobga olib va kvadratura formularini birini qo‘llash natijasida $x(t)$ va $u(t)$ izlayotgan funksiyalarning sonli qiymatlarini topish uchun (6) ko‘rinishdagi algoritmgga ega bo‘ldik.

PROGRAMMA KODI (KOD ПРОГРАММЫ):

Kiruvchi parametrlar (Входные параметры)

$nn:=100$ tugun nuqtalar soni (kolichestvo uzlovых tochek)

$h:=0.01$ qadam (shag)

Berilgan integro- differensial tenglamalar sistemasining koeffitsientlari

Koeffitsienty zadannoy sistem integro-differensialных uravneniy

$\alpha_1 := 0.1$ $\alpha_2 := 0.2$ $\beta_1 := 0.5$ $\beta_2 := 0.3$ $\varepsilon_1 := 0.2$ $\varepsilon_2 := 0.1$

$a_1 := 1$ $a_2 := 2$ $\beta_3 := 0.4$ $b_1 := 3$ $b_2 := 4$ $\beta_4 := 0.2$

$$A_0 := 1 \quad A_1 := -\beta_1 \quad A_2 := (\beta_1)^2 \quad A_3 := -(\beta_1)^3 \quad B_2 := (\beta_2)^2 \\ B_3 := -(\beta_2)^3 \quad B_0 := 1 \quad B_1 := -\beta_2$$

Parametrlar boshlang'ich qiymatlari (Nachalnye znacheniya parametrov)

$$p0 := \frac{h^{\alpha_1}}{2} * \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\alpha_1} \quad p0 = 0.631 \quad r0 := \frac{h^{\alpha_2}}{2} * \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\alpha_2} \quad r0 = 0.1$$

$$pm_0 := p0 \quad rm_0 := r0 \quad pj_0 := p0 \quad rm_0 := r0 \quad t_0 := 0$$

$$e1_0 := 1 \quad e2_0 := 1 \quad pm_0 := 0.631 \quad rm_0 := 0.1 \quad a3_0 := 1 \quad b3_0 := 1$$

$$f1_0 := a_1 * (\beta_1)^4 + a_2 * (\beta_2)^4 + a3_0 \quad f1_0 = 6.362$$

$$f2_0 := b_1 * (\beta_1)^4 + b_2 * (\beta_2)^4 + b3_0 \quad f2_0 = 3.361$$

Вычислениа znacheniya uzlovykh tochek, tochnykh resheniy, pravyyh chastey, peremennykh koeffitsientov i shagi kvadrurnykh formul

Tugun nuqtalar, aniq yechim, o'ng tomon, o'zgaruvchi koeffitsientlar qiymatlari va kvadratura formulalari qadamlarini hisoblash

$$i := 1..nn$$

$$t_i := i * h \quad \text{tugun nuqtalar (uzlovye tochky)}$$

Aniq yechimlar qiymatlari (Znacheniya tochnykh resheniy)

$$e1_i := \exp(-\beta_1 * t_i)$$

$$e2_i := \exp(-\beta_2 * t_i)$$

O'zgaruvchi koeffitsientlar qiymatlari (Znacheniya peremennykh koeffitsientov)

$$a3_i := \exp(-\beta_3 * t_i)$$

$$b3_i := \exp(-\beta_4 * t_i)$$

O'ng tomon qiymatlari (Znacheniya pravyyh chastey)

$$f1_i := a_1 * (\beta_1)^4 * e1_i + a_2 * (\beta_2)^4 * e2_i + a3_i \left[1 - \frac{\varepsilon_1}{\alpha_1} * (t_i)^{\alpha_1} \right] * e1_i$$

$$f2_i := b_1 * (\beta_1)^4 * e1_i + b_2 * (\beta_2)^4 * e2_i + b3_i \left[1 - \frac{\varepsilon_2}{\alpha_2} * (t_i)^{\alpha_2} \right] * e2_i$$

Kvadratura formulalari qadamlari (Shagi kvadrurnykh formul)

$$pj_i := p0 * [i^{\alpha_1} - (i-1)^{\alpha_1}] * e1_i$$

$$pm_1 := p0 * [(i+1)^{\alpha_1} - (i-1)^{\alpha_1}] * e1_i$$

$$rj_i := p0 * [i^{\alpha_2} - (i-1)^{\alpha_2}] * e2_i$$

$$rm_i := p0 * [(i + 1)^{\alpha_2} - (i - 1)^{\alpha_2}] * e2_i$$

Izlanayotgan yechimlar qiymatlari (Znacheniya iskomыx resheniya) $U :=$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & x_0 \leftarrow 1 \\
 & y_0 \leftarrow 1 \\
 & \text{for } n \in 1..nn \\
 & \quad s1x \leftarrow 0 \\
 & \quad s1y \leftarrow 0 \\
 & \quad \text{for } j \in 0..n - 1 \\
 & \quad \quad c_j \leftarrow h \\
 & \quad \quad c_0 \leftarrow \frac{h}{2} \\
 & \quad \quad s2x \leftarrow 0 \\
 & \quad \quad s2y \leftarrow 0 \\
 & \quad \quad \text{for } m \in 0..j \\
 & \quad \quad \quad p_m \leftarrow pm_m \\
 & \quad \quad \quad p_j \leftarrow pj_m \\
 & \quad \quad \quad p_0 \leftarrow p0 \\
 & \quad \quad \quad r_m \leftarrow rm_m \\
 & \quad \quad \quad r_j \leftarrow rj_m \\
 & \quad \quad \quad r_0 \leftarrow r0 \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s2x \leftarrow s2x + p_m * (x_{j-m})^3 \\
 & \quad \quad \quad s2y \leftarrow s2y + r_m * (y_{j-m})^3 \\
 & \quad \quad s1x \leftarrow s1x + c_j * \frac{(t_n - t_j)^3}{6} * [f1_j - a3_j * [(x_j)^3 - s2x]] \\
 & \quad \quad s1y \leftarrow s1y + c_j * \frac{(t_n - t_j)^3}{6} * [f2_j - b3_j * [(y_j)^3 - s2y]] \\
 & s1x \leftarrow s1x + a_1 * A_0 + a_1 * A_1 * t_n + a_1 * A_2 * \frac{(t_n)^2}{2} + a_1 * A_3 * \frac{(t_n)^3}{6} + \\
 & \quad + a_2 * B_0 + a_2 * B_1 * t_n + a_2 * B_2 * \frac{(t_n)^2}{2} + a_2 * B_3 * \frac{(t_n)^3}{6} \\
 & s1y \leftarrow s1y + b_1 * A_0 + b_1 * A_1 * t_n + b_1 * A_2 * \frac{(t_n)^2}{2} + b_1 * A_3 * \frac{(t_n)^3}{6} + \\
 & \quad + b_2 * B_0 + b_2 * B_1 * t_n + b_2 * B_2 * \frac{(t_n)^2}{2} + b_2 * B_3 * \frac{(t_n)^3}{6} \\
 & x_n \leftarrow \frac{b_2 * s1x - a_2 * s1y}{a_1 * b_2 - a_2 * b_1} \\
 & y_n \leftarrow \frac{b_1 * s1x - a_1 * s1y}{a_2 * b_1 - a_1 * b_2}
 \end{aligned}$$

XULOSA: Shuni ta’kidlash mumkinki ilmiy-tatqiqot ishlarida kompyuter matematikasi tizimlarining va maqolada keltirilgan algoritm hamda dasturning qo‘llanishi ko‘pgina muammolarning hal etilishida katta yordam beradi.

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